

NATURAL WAY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH LISTENING COMPREHENSION AND READING COMPREHENSION

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Abstract

People acquire special kinds of knowledge over their lifetime, and especially by active study. But of course, it is not enough for a human simply to put in challenging work and talent to learn foreign languages; it is also necessary to do it in a proper way that is strictly consistent with human nature in order for individuals to be able to learn in the most efficient way. The present methodology of foreign language learning proposes one very efficient and effortless way of learning by engaging the learners in listening comprehension of live speech and, at a later stage, by reading comprehension, aiming learners to develop an understanding of unfamiliar words' meaning from the context and to memorize language, as well as to enhance speaking abilities in a natural way.

Keywords: Foreign language comprehension by listening and reading; Foreign word memorization; native language; listening, reading, speaking, writing in a foreign language; grammar, lexicology; the language of thought; passive language knowledge; active language knowledge; levels of language knowledge; fluency in a foreign language.

Research in Support of Modern Foreign Language Learning

1. Introduction

Language is the oldest intellectual skill that humans have ever mastered. Its knowledge is an indicator of the level of intellectual ability of the speaker. We can hardly imagine human thought without language, although it is in principle possible. Apart from scientifically proven examples of the possible existence of human thought without any linguistic signs, human thought and language are two sides of the same whole, like two sides of a "coin". It is known that the five senses through which a person perceives the world are: sight, hearing, smell, taste, and sensation (the so-called perception systems). Humans can perceive through one or more perceptions in a combination of senses. Success in learning a language depends on human attention and on how the human mind receives linguistic information. Learners master foreign languages by permanent memorization and by exercises for understanding and speaking. In addition, languages are also involved in the human thought process. The author's point of view is that *the pattern of language learning is the same no matter what the language is, whether it be a native language or a foreign language.*

The current methodology for learning foreign languages is based on the natural way of learning them. In addition, to speed up the learning process and shorten the time to reach the desired level of proficiency, the methodology includes a scholastic way of teaching but is highly streamlined.

The natural way to learn a foreign language is by listening to live speech, accompanied by observing the environment and the facial expression of the speaker, i.e., the learners must "immerse themselves in the waters" of the foreign language which they study. It is especially important to note that in the initial stage of learning a foreign language, it is necessary to listen to foreign speech for a long time with a level of complex-

ity corresponding to the learner's knowledge. Subsequently, when the learner has already created his passive vocabulary of foreign words, in parallel with listening to foreign speech, the learner should go on with reading texts with a complexity corresponding to the level of the learner's knowledge, i.e., listening and reading texts with appropriate difficulty is the basis of natural acquisition of foreign languages. In parallel with listening to a speech and reading a text in the studied foreign language, learners must translate the vocabulary and do grammar exercises, but only of what they have repeatedly heard and memorized at a proper level. Gradual progress in the studied material, with consistent and multiple repetition of what learners have already learned, contributes to the permanent memorization of the learned language units. Learners of a foreign language should repeat what they have learned because each subsequent time of repetition improves the memorization of the language.

❖ Definition for language: *A system of signs for expression and exchange of human beings' thoughts by four language skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing. Language gives people the ability to think and to communicate with each other.*

2. Human Intelligence, Human Memory, Methodology of Study, and Their Impact on Foreign Language Learning

❖ Definition for Human Intelligence: *The ability to think, to learn from experience, to solve problems, and to adapt to new situations is a variable more strongly related to successful educational, occupational, economic, and social outcomes than any other individual differences in human intellectual abilities.*

❖ Definition for Human Memory: *Human memory is the psychological process of acquiring, storing, retaining, and later retrieving information. There are three major processes involved in memory: encoding, storage, and retrieval.*

❖ Definition for Methodology of Study: *The definition of the methodology of study is the most efficient way to obtain certain useful knowledge for the same to be used in human life.*

2.1. Memory as Categories, Phases, and Functions
Below table characterize human memory in terms of categories, phases, and functions.

Table 1

Model Conceptualized in Terms of Type, Stages and Processes ¹	
Categories, Phases and Functions of Human Memory	
Categories	Explicit memory
	Implicit memory
Phases	Sensory memory
	Short-term memory
	Long-term memory
Functions	Encoding
	Storage
	Retrieve

The Human Memory Model is important for the creation of efficient educational methodologies. Memory is one of the mysteries of the human mind for which researchers do not yet have a comprehensive answer. Richard Atkinson and Richard Shiffrin developed the three-component model of memory in 1968. The researchers described memory as a system with three main components: sensory memory, short-term memory (also known as working memory), and long-term memory. Since then, it has become one of the main models used to describe the inner workings of memory. (Theodore T, 2022)²

2.1.1. Categories of memory:

❖ Explicit memory

When we try ourselves or ask somebody else to remember something that has happened before, this is related to explicit memory. Explicit memory is the experience we have accumulated before, e.g., a recollection of a life experience we had previously.

❖ Implicit memory

While explicit memory refers to things that we can consciously recall, implicit memory refers to knowledge that we cannot recall. *Implicit memory refers to the influence of experience on behavior, even if the individual is not aware of those influences.* (Walinga, 2010)³

2.1.2. Phases of Memory

The three phases of human memory are sensory, short-term memory, and long-term memory. All these three phases of memory are important for human thought activity, so it is necessary for learners to be familiar with human memory division. From the point of view of learning a second (foreign) language, all these three phases of memory we must consider when we create foreign language learning methodologies. (R. C. Atkinson, 1968)⁴

Phases of Memory: Sensory, Short-Term, and Long-Term Memory

¹ Ch. Stangor and J. Walinga, (2010), Introduction to Psychology – 1st Canadian Edition, e-ISBN: 978-1-77420-005-6, p.362

² Theodore T. (2022), Atkinson and Shiffrin Model of Memory (Multi-Store Model), Practical Psychology, <https://practicalpie.com/atkinson-shiffrin-modal-model-of-memory/>

³ Charles Stanger, Jennifer Walinga (2010), Introduction to Psychology – 1st Canadian Edition, e-ISBN: 978-1-77420-005-6 p.362/3

⁴ R. C. Atkinson and R. M. Shiffrin (1968), Human Memory: a Proposed System and its control process, Stanford University, California, p.94,96,103

Fig.1: Memory duration⁵

2.1.2.1. Sensory memory: this type of memory appears in the initial stage of memorization and is negligible, it can last for few a seconds. Depending on the person's five senses, the sensory memory is visual, auditory, gustatory, olfactory, and tactile. For language learning, it is important for auditory sensory memory, known as echoic memory (Cowan, Lichty,&Grove, 1990), and visual sensory memory, known as iconic memory (George Sperling, 1960).⁶

2.1.2.2. Short-term Memory: This type of memory is short-lived and stores various images, words, numbers, and facts from few seconds to a few minutes. Short-term memory can be reproduced easily but can be displaced easily by new information. The information we pay attention to goes into our short-term memory. For language learning, it is important to say

that all foreign language learned words go to short-term memory first. This information cannot stay there permanently but stays in the brain for a very few seconds, usually less than a minute. Short-term memory is also known as working memory.

❖ Short-term memory has three key aspects:⁷

- *It has limited capacity* - it can store about seven items (letters, numbers, words, pictures, names) at a time.
- *It has limited duration* - it is very fragile, and the information can be lost with distraction or the passage of time.

Encoding is primarily acoustic, even translating visual information into sounds.

Figure 2: Short-Term Memory Decay

On Fig.2—Decay of Short-term Memory, we can see when we store information in short-term memory

and then it will be lost if we do not refresh it properly and enough.⁸

⁵ Charles Stango, Jennifer Walinga (2010), Introduction to Psychology – 1st Canadian Edition, e-ISBN: 978-1-77420-005-6, p.366

⁶ Charles Stango, Jennifer Walinga (2010), Introduction to Psychology – 1st Canadian Edition, e-ISBN: 978-1-77420-005-, p.367

⁷ Dr.McLeod S. A. (2009, December 14). *Short-term memory*, *Simply Psychology*. www.simplypsychology.org/short-term-memory.htm

⁸ Peterson L, Peterson MJ. Short-term retention of individual verbal items. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*. 1959;58:193–198. doi: 10.1037/h0049234.

One way to prevent the decay of information in short-term memory is to refresh it in order not to lose it and later to make the transition of the information to long-term memory. Refreshment of information (maintenance rehearsal) is a process of repeating information mentally with the goal of keeping it in memory. We must refresh the information when we want to remember it (e.g., person names, phone numbers, addresses) to write it down or potentially transfer it to long-term memory.

2.1.2.3. Long-term Memory: This type of memory is long-lasting, and the information stored in it can be reproduced after a lengthy period, such as years. The recovery of memory may take seconds until all the necessary parts of the brain activate.^{9,10}

3. Four types of skills for mastering a foreign language

The basic skills needed to master any foreign language are listening, reading, speaking, and writing. We can divide these four skills into two groups:

- Listening and reading to comprehend the concepts presented in the foreign language. These two skills are necessary to understand the spoken and written language; they are the so-called input skills (input info.).¹¹

- Speaking and writing a foreign language is our ability to present our or another person's thoughts in a foreign language. These two skills are necessary to express ourselves in the spoken and written language; they are the so-called output skills (output info.).¹²

4. Characteristics of the learning process of four language skills

The characteristics of four language skills: listening, reading, speaking, and writing, listed in this order, are as follows:

- This ranking is determined by the difficulty of learning. Listening and understanding are the easiest to learn. Then comes reading, and after that, speaking and writing, respectively.

- It is reasonable to assume that we must first learn to understand the language before we can express ourselves in it. The opposite is impossible.¹³

When learning a foreign language, one must always follow the order of skills that are necessary for its acquisition. The opposite is a waste of time and effort.

5. Preparation of the state of mind when learning a foreign language

Learning a foreign language is a voluntary intellectual process requiring sustained attention and full concentration of the mind on the part of learners. One can control one's actions thanks to the mind, but controlling one's attention is not an easy task. The mind is not an "automatic machine," and control of attention can be achieved through self-control and the habit of listening attentively. Along with the attention and concentration of the mind as another key factor for the easy perception and learning of foreign languages, we should also point out the physical condition of the learner, whether he has rested, and the presence of any emotional disturbances. The above factors are controllable, i.e., the learner can create the best conditions for learning. Along with these controllable factors, the learner's interest in learning the foreign language is also necessary. This is an important condition for success because humans can only learn a foreign language with a great desire for and love for the language.

6. Ways to learn a second (foreign) language

- A natural way of learning the native and second (foreign) languages.

- The traditional (scholastic) method of learning a second (foreign) language through an organized form of learning with teacher participation.

- Modern methods of learning a second (foreign) language: in this field, enormous work has been done, and various methods have been created. Linguistics considers that language learning is an individual act and that different learners may benefit from different methodologies. On the other hand, human minds and

⁹ Article by Kendra Chaerry (2021), What is Long-Term Memory, verywellmind, <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-long-term-memory-2795347>

¹⁰ Article „Long-Term Memory”, The Human Memory (2022), <https://human-memory.net/long-term-memory/>

¹¹ Article „The importance of input in the ELT classroom”, Cambridge University Press, <https://www.cambridge.org/elt/blog/2017/12/19/the-importance-of-input-in-the-elt-classroom/>

¹² Article „Input and output in second language”, My English Pages, <https://www.myenglishpages.com/blog/input-and-output-in-second-language-acquisition/>

¹³ Article „The Four Basic Language Skills”, Columbia Gorge, Community College, <https://www.cgcc.edu/literacy/resources/four-basic-language-skills>

psychology are the same. That is why science still has to do more in general to improve foreign language learning.

7. Foreign Language Learning by Listening Comprehension and Reading Comprehension

The first main element of the current methodology is learning the language first through listening comprehension, with parallel learning of the vocabulary from the text, through reading, translation, and learning the relevant grammatical units from the text. This methodology is suitable for beginners at language level A1.¹⁴

The second main element of the current methodology is "reading comprehension"¹⁵ and it has to be practiced in parallel with the continued learning of the language by "listening comprehension"¹⁶, i.e., "listening comprehension" and "reading comprehension"¹⁷, together with the parallel learning of the vocabulary from the text, by reading and learning the corresponding grammatical unit from the text. This methodology is suitable for beginners at language level A2.

The third element of the methodology is the learning of grammar in small steps, but each new grammar unit involves a repetition of the previous study. Teachers must add new and more complex forms, if necessary, i.e., grammar must be taught gradually and at several levels. Each grammar level includes the previous levels but, in all cases, emphasizes the current level most. This rule is valid for all levels A1-C1, but of course the students should emphasize their weak points.

The fourth element of the methodology is a proper balance between the learning of unfamiliar words and the study of new grammar rules. In this way, learners improve their weak side of language command.

The fifth and most essential element of the methodology is the proportions of time for listening, reading, speaking, and writing, as these are the basic skills necessary for mastering any foreign language. In this fifth and most essential element of the foreign language learning methodology, the learner can improve one or some basic skills involving proficiency in the foreign language.

8. The process of learning unfamiliar words in a foreign language

Learning any foreign language is a process that takes place over a period, which can be divided into distinct stages. For learners, knowing this process is necessary to choose the most efficient way of learning each word. An improper way of learning foreign words leads to ineffective memorization. As a result of inefficient learning, learners waste time that could be used to acquire more knowledge. For individual words, especially those in which learners have a personal interest, they can memorize very quickly, even with 1-2 readings and translation, but for most, this is not the case.

Very often, learners must translate the same words multiple times to memorize them. This is normal, but it may be because of learning unfamiliar words incorrectly. Learners cannot complete the memorization of foreign words with only one study. The multi-level study of foreign words (vocabulary) takes place in several stages and for different periods of time. The present methodology considers multilevel learning of unfamiliar words.

9. Stages of foreign language word learning

Unfamiliar foreign words can be heard in speeches or read in text.

- When learners hear a word in a speech, they must hear it distinctly. New unfamiliar words should be correctly perceived and later correctly pronounced.

- When learners come across an unfamiliar word in a text, they should look it up in a dictionary. It is also good to hear an audio recording of the same word. There are dictionaries that provide this option, like Google Translate. It is desirable to use dictionaries from reputable publishers.¹⁸

- Unfamiliar foreign words can be learnt in a proper multistage way of learning.

10. Strategies for speaking fluently in a foreign language

The main goal of strategies for learning a foreign language is to achieve the desired result (level of language proficiency) in the most efficient way possible—minimally spending time necessary for learning the study material up to the desired level of foreign language proficiency. No matter what the learners' plans are regarding the desired level of foreign language proficiency, learners need to pass through certain stages of language learning. The achievement of the goal is possible through appropriate training methodology and proper planning of training material for each of the training stages. If learners want to achieve the best possible level, then they must go through certain successive levels. In this case, it is particularly important that the planned learning material refers only to the current level, i.e., the learner should not study higher-level and difficult material. The reason for this is to study only the learning materials for the current level as quickly and best as possible because this is the only way to achieve the desired intermediate results and goals as quickly as possible. The advantage of this strategy is that the learner will be able to start actively using the language sooner. A language has two main levels of proficiency – passive and active. The border between the two main ways of mastering a foreign language is when learners begin to express themselves and conduct a dialogue in the foreign language without making a preliminary mental translation. This moment of "speaking" the foreign language is like the moment when children start to speak their native language. This second

¹⁴ Article "What is Listening Comprehension", All about Learning press, <https://blog.allaboutlearningpress.com/listening-comprehension/>

¹⁵ Article "Improve your students' Reading Comprehension," (5 July 2022), <https://readtheory.org/>

¹⁶ Article "What is Listening Comprehension", All about Learning press, <https://blog.allaboutlearningpress.com/listening-comprehension>

¹⁷ Research paper by Marcelo, Paul Bernal, using reading to teach English as a foreign language, MASKANA, Vol.11, No.2, 18-26, <https://publicaciones.ucuenca.edu.ec/ojs/index.php/maskana/article/view/3451>
doi: 10.18537/mskn.11.02.02

¹⁸ Article „Learning new words”, British Council, <https://learnenglishteens.britishcouncil.org/exams/grammar-vocabulary-exams/learning-new-words>

stage of language learning, after the learners are able to hold a conversation, is called the beginning of language fluency.

❖ From a practical point of view, we can divide proficiency in foreign languages into three levels:

- Conversational level-requires a vocabulary of at least one thousand words, basic verb tenses, and the most important parts of grammar, as well as the ability to hold a conversation on everyday topics.

- Fluency in the language requires knowledge of a vocabulary of at least three thousand words, verb tenses, and basic grammar, as well as the ability to hold a fluent dialogue on any topic.

- Expert level: requires knowledge of a vocabulary of at least twelve thousand words, complex forms of verb tenses and the rest of the grammar required for a sophisticated speaking style, as well as the ability to translate on any topic.¹⁹

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